

INTRODUCTION AND TRAINING ON GOOGLE SITE AS A DIGITAL PORTFOLIO FOR STUDENTS AT SMK PGRI 16 JAKARTA

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Abstrak

In the current digital era, the ability to master information technology is an essential skill that must be possessed by every individual, including students. Introduction and training activities on the use of Google Sites as a digital portfolio are very important and provide great benefits, especially in helping students display their work and academic achievements in a professional and efficient way. This activity is designed to implement a Google Sites introduction and training program for students of SMK PGRI 16 Jakarta, aimed at improving their digital literacy skills and preparing them to face the challenges of the digital age. The approach taken in this activity is through practical training methods carried out interactively, accompanied by question and answer sessions to ensure a comprehensive understanding of the material provided. The results of this activity show a significant increase in students' abilities in creating and managing digital portfolios via Google Sites. This not only enhances their skills in information technology, but also provides them with an effective tool to present themselves and their work to a wider audience. From this activity, it can be seen that the integration of information technology in the world of education, especially through the use of Google Sites as a digital portfolio media, has great potential in increasing digital literacy and the readiness of students and students for future careers.

Kata kunci — Google Sites, digital portfolio, digital literacy, vocational education, SMK PGRI 16 Jakarta

Introduction

In the digital era that continues to develop, digital literacy skills are one of the critical aspects that must be possessed by the younger generation, especially for students at educational institutions such as SMK PGRI 16 Jakarta. Recognizing the importance of preparing students with relevant skills for the future, the introduction and training in the use of Google Sites as a tool for creating digital portfolios is an important initiative. Google Sites, with its user-friendly interface and high accessibility, offers an effective solution to address the digital literacy gap. This community service activity aims to increase the digital literacy of students and students through practical training in creating and managing digital portfolios, which not only allows them to display their work and achievements professionally but also prepares them for competition in the digital era.

According to the revelation of Sindu Prasetya et al, Google sites are personal or professional website services created by the Google company that do not charge any fees or are free. Previous community service has discussed a lot about the use of Google Sites, such as to create digital learning media[1].

According to Syukron Al Azhar, many livestock entrepreneurs have felt the various benefits of using Google sites as a marketing medium in the era of the Covid-19 pandemic, so activities are needed that can increase sales, such as teachers can use Google sites because it is easy to use and has minimal costs (only internet connection costs)[2].

According to Joko Waluyo, Google sites is one of the website media that can be used in the learning process. Google sites is a website that is used for group or personal purposes. Google Sites is the easiest way to make information accessible to people who need it quickly, and people can work together

on the site to add attached files and information from other Google applications such as Google Docs, Sheets, Forms, Calendar, Awesome Table. and so forth[3].

According to Roberto Kaban et al, Google Sites is a way the easiest way to make information accessible to people who need it quickly, and people can work together on the site to add file attachments as well as information from other Google applications such as Google Docs, Sheets, Forms and so on[4]. According to Susilawati et al, training to create digital marketing websites provides students with special skills, so they can manage their skills as a source of life[5].

According to Eko Kuntarto et al, digital portfolios are an alternative for teachers in optimizing learning and assessment of students. Portfolio This digital is a digital collection displayed systematically inside a personal website, portfolio creation digital can be done using Googlesites application, where teachers can fill in useful content such as lesson plans, modules Teaching, LKPD, learning media, and also assessment[6].

This activity is designed with a methodology that integrates theory and practice, where students will gain an understanding of the concept of digital portfolios and digital literacy, followed by practical training sessions using Google Sites. It is hoped that this workshop will encourage active participation from students in the learning process, supported by competent facilitators, who not only provide technical guidance but also ensure that each participant can apply the knowledge gained. Through evaluating portfolios created by students, this activity aims to ensure effective understanding and application of the concepts and skills taught.

The expected impact of this community service activity is very broad, not only limited to increasing students' abilities in digital literacy, but also in terms of their self-confidence to face challenges in the world of work and education which is increasingly

dependent on digital technology. It is also hoped that this activity will stimulate other educational institutions to integrate digital literacy into their curriculum, thereby helping to provide students with the tools and knowledge necessary for success in the future. Through this initiative, it is hoped that a young generation can be created that is not only adaptive to technological changes, but is also able to become a pioneer in shaping an inclusive and sustainable digital future.

Devotion Method

1.Preperation

The first step is to map the needs and potential of partners. This step involves surveys and initial discussions with the school, including teachers, staff and students, to identify specific needs and potential for further development. Next, training materials are prepared. The training materials are designed according to students' needs and level of understanding, covering the basics of creating digital portfolios, using Google Sites, and visual communication design principles.

The service team then divides tasks based on the expertise of each member. The project coordinator will manage the schedule, logistics, and communication between all parties. Technical instructors, who are IT and web design experts, are responsible for technical training on the use of Google Sites. Content instructors, who are content and communications specialists, will assist students in developing engaging portfolio materials. The facilitator is tasked with encouraging active student participation and facilitating discussion and question and answer sessions.

2.Implementation

Activities began by holding a series of training workshops that actively involved students in learning the theory and practice of creating digital portfolios using Google Sites. After the workshop, it continues with mentoring sessions provided both face-to-

face and online to help students apply the knowledge and skills they have learned. Active participation from partners, namely students and teachers, is highly expected. Students actively participate in all training sessions, provide feedback, and apply learnings in the creation of their digital portfolios. Teachers act as facilitators of learning in the classroom, supporting the implementation of the digital literacy curriculum, and integrating this learning with other subjects.

3. Evaluation and Monitoring

The first step is to assess and evaluate the digital portfolio that has been created by the student. This process involves providing constructive feedback to help students make further improvements. In addition, feedback was collected from students and teachers regarding the effectiveness of the training and areas requiring improvement. This input will be the basis for identifying program strengths and weaknesses, as well as for designing future improvement steps.

4. Continuous Development

The first step is to form a community of practice among students, teachers and service teams. This community aims to share experiences, resources and strengthen support networks in digital literacy. Next, a follow-up plan is prepared based on the evaluation results and feedback that has been collected. This plan includes continued training or adjustments to training materials to ensure that the program remains relevant and effective in improving participants' digital literacy skills.

Results and Discussion

Community service activities carried out at SMK PGRI 16 Jakarta succeeded in achieving its main objective, namely increasing digital literacy and students' ability to create digital portfolios using Google Sites. Through a series of workshops and mentoring sessions, students can understand the concept of digital portfolios,

learn how to create and manage their own websites, and apply creative designs to display their work. This activity attracted high interest from students and students, with total participation reaching 45 participants. Their enthusiasm is clearly visible from their active participation in every training session and discussion, showing their seriousness in learning and applying the digital portfolio concept for self-development and future careers.

One of the most significant outcomes of this activity is increased digital literacy among participants. Before carrying out the activity, many participants were not familiar with the concept and practice of creating a digital portfolio. However, after following a series of systematic and practical training, participants demonstrated a significant increase in competency in using Google Sites to create and manage their own digital portfolios. Evaluation of participants' abilities before and after training showed an average increase of 40% in digital literacy.

Each participant successfully created a digital portfolio that reflects their work, achievements and aspirations. This portfolio not only provides a means for participants to express themselves and their creativity but also serves as an effective tool for educational and professional purposes, such as college applications or job searches. Feedback from participants and teachers at SMK PGRI 16 Jakarta was very positive. They recognize the significant added value of having the skills to create a digital portfolio and appreciate the opportunity this activity provides to learn and develop these skills.

This activity was successfully documented through photos, videos and the publication of participants' digital portfolios on the school website. This not only increases the visibility of students' work but also encourages recognition and appreciation from the school community and general public of their achievements. Documentation

of community service activities with the title "Introduction and Training on Google Sites as a Digital Portfolio for Students at SMK PGRI 16 Jakarta" reflects the commitment and success of this program in developing students' digital skills.

Figure 1. Group photo with the School Principal and PkM Team

Figure 2. Introduction to Google Site for students at SMK PGRI 16 Jakarta

Figure 3. Giving Memories to the School

Figure 4. Training for students regarding creating a website as a digital portfolio

Conclusion

The PKM activity "Introduction and Training on Google Site as a Digital Portfolio for Students at SMK PGRI 16 Jakarta" has succeeded in achieving its goal of increasing digital literacy and introducing the concept of digital portfolios to students. The results of this activity show the importance of using information technology in education and preparing students to face an increasingly digital world. Through this activity, students not only gain new skills but also a platform to present themselves and their work to the

outside world, opening up more opportunities for their career and educational development in the future.

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